

Comparative study of Cd-free Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ solar cells with amorphous In₂O₃:H and ZnO:Al front contact layers.

Diego A. Garzon¹, Marina Alves^{1,2}, Pedro Sousa¹, José Fonseca¹, Daniel Brito¹, Joaquim Carneiro², Sascha Sadewasser¹

(1) International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory, Av. Mestre José Veiga s/n, Braga 4715-330, Portugal.

(2) Centre of Physics of Minho and Porto Universities (CF-UM-UP), Azurém Campus, Guimarães 4800-058, Portugal.

Abstract

Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ (CIGSe) thin-film solar cells are known as a promising solution for the current energy challenge. However, the environmental and health concerns associated with the conventional use of toxic CdS buffer layers, along with the limitations posed by the conductivity of commonly used ZnO:Al (AZO), require further innovation for new alternatives. It was shown independently that both layers can be replaced for non-toxic and highly conductive layers, such as zinc-tin oxide (Zn_{1-x}Sn_xO_y, ZTO) and hydrogen-doped indium oxide (In₂O₃:H, IOH), respectively. Thus, this study presents a strategic modification by replacing the CdS buffer layer with ZTO, deposited by chemical bath deposition, and the AZO front contact with highly conductive IOH. Our IOH-based solar cells display higher fill factor and open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}), though lower short-circuit current compared to AZO-based devices. Notably, the ZTO/IOH-based solar cell achieved a maximum power conversion efficiency (PCE) of 11.5 %, with a V_{oc} of 607 mV, while the best device for the CdS/IOH-based solar cell reached a PCE of 13.5 %, with a V_{oc} of 633 mV. Therefore, we demonstrate the viability of scalable and cost-effective deposition methods for both buffer and front contact layers in CIGSe solar cells, offering comparable performance to conventional layers reported in the literature.

Introduction

Second-generation Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ (CIGSe)-based solar cells are considered a promising photovoltaic technology due to their high efficiency, cost-effectiveness and various fabrication methods.¹ In general, CIGSe solar cells have a substrate-type configuration consisting of substrate/back contact/CIGSe/buffer/transparent conductive oxide (TCO). Sometimes an antireflective coating and metallic contacts are used to finish the device. For the substrate, soda-lime glass (SLG) is commonly used, which remains inert and stable during the deposition process but also acts as a Na supplier for the CIGSe absorber, enhancing the solar cell performance.^{2,3} For the back contact, Mo is used because it functions as a reflector and is relatively inert during the CIGSe deposition.¹ The p-type CIGSe absorber has several benefits, including a tuneable direct bandgap, high absorption coefficient, lower material usage compared to Si solar cells, and diverse deposition methods.¹

On top of the CIGSe absorber layer, an n-type CdS buffer layer is typically deposited forming a p-n junction with the absorber. At this junction the charge carriers are separated and later collected by the contact layers.⁴ CIGSe solar cells with CdS buffer

layer have achieved a record efficiency of 23.6%.⁵ CdS is used due to its electrical properties and structural matching with the absorber. Furthermore, this layer is normally deposited by chemical bath deposition (CBD) due to the beneficial effect of ammonia on the passivation of the CIGSe surface and to ensure a complete and conformal coverage over the polycrystalline absorber.^{6,7} However, due to the toxicity and narrow bandgap associated with CdS, alternative materials have been explored as buffers.^{5,8–10} Among these materials, zinc tin oxide ($Zn_xSn_{1-x}O_y$, ZTO) has been widely studied due to its high transparency, non-toxicity, fast light responsivity, and tuneable wide bandgap.^{11–13} In a recent study, we presented a CBD route for ZTO deposition, investigating the impact of the Sn-to-Zn ratio in solution ($TTZ = [Sn]/([Sn]+[Zn])$). Our findings indicated optimal performance at 20% TTZ, equivalent to approximately 12% TTZ in the film, with a similar power conversion efficiency (PCE) as CdS references.¹²

The implementation of front contacts with high transmittance, good conductivity, and low resistance is essential for CIGSe solar cells. Transparent conductive oxides (TCOs) have emerged as promising candidates for such electrodes in various optoelectronic applications, including solar cells. Notably, aluminum-doped zinc oxide (AZO) represents an intentionally doped TCO utilizing zinc oxide—a cost-effective, non-toxic, and abundant material.^{14,15} AZO exhibits a large direct bandgap ($E_g = 3.5$ eV)¹⁶ and a high transparency across the visible spectrum and near-infrared (NIR) range, making it an ideal candidate for front contacts.¹⁷ Additionally, indium oxide is a well-established material that, when doped with H_2O or H_2 , forms highly transparent and conductive thin films, referred to as hydrogen-doped indium oxide (IOH). IOH has been thoroughly investigated by Koida et al., due to its high conductivity, small dispersion of refractive index and very low extinction coefficient in the visible to the NIR wavelengths.¹⁸ Both AZO and IOH have been effectively employed as front contacts in CIGSe thin film solar cells.^{18–21}

Here, we present the fabrication of CIGSe solar cells with ZTO and IOH as buffer and front contact layers, respectively. This with the objective of finding the compatibility between these two alternatives for the traditional structure of thin film solar cells with less toxic elements, for the buffer, and high conductivity TCO for the case of the front contact.

Experimental section

Fabrication of thin-film solar cells:

For the solar cell fabrication, industry-grade CIGSe absorbers supplied by Nice Solar GmbH were employed. These absorbers have shown a PCE of 15.6%.²² These samples consist of a soda-lime glass substrate with a thin layer (500 nm) of molybdenum as back contact, followed by a layer of around 2–3 μm of CIGSe on top and a protective layer of CdS. The latter was etched away with an acid treatment (~9% HCl) for 90s. Immediately after, the buffer layer was deposited by chemical bath deposition (CdS or ZTO). For the CdS, a sequential mixture of ammonium hydroxide solution (100mL, 4.2%), cadmium acetate solution (25mL, 22.6 mM), and thiourea solution (50mL, 0.35 M) was used. The bath was set at 60°C, and the sample was

immersed for 8.5 minutes. For the ZTO buffer layer, the deposition bath was prepared by consecutive addition of aliquots of ZnSO₄, NH₄OH, ethanolamine, and SnCl₂ stock solutions to obtain a final concentration of 75 mM of cations ([Zn²⁺] + [Sn²⁺]), 0.2 M NH₄OH, and 1.6 M ethanolamine.¹² The deposition was done at 92°C for 30 minutes, with a TTZ of 20%.

To finalize the solar cells, a double window layer was deposited on top of the buffer by radio-frequency (RF) magnetron sputtering, at room temperature, in the sputtering for advanced research (STAR) system.²² First, an intrinsic ZnO layer was deposited at 5.6×10⁻³ mbar Ar pressure with 40 W (2.0 W cm⁻²) for 21 min (thickness around 50 nm). Subsequently, a conductive layer of either ZnO:Al or In₂O₃:H was deposited. The ZnO:Al layer was deposited at 2.7×10⁻³ mbar Ar pressure with 60 W (3.0 W cm⁻²) for 57 min (~300 nm). The In₂O₃:H was deposited from a 2-inch ceramic In₂O₃ target, and hydrogen doping was obtained by inserting a gas mixture of Ar/H₂ (5% H₂). The total working pressure (Ar, Ar/H₂, and O₂) was 5.3×10⁻³ mbar with 20 W (1.0 W cm⁻²) for 120 min (~300nm). The oxygen flow was pulsed into the system for one minute every two minutes, to achieve a low oxygen content in the sputtering atmosphere.²³

In addition, to study the optical and electrical properties of the window stack and the individual front contacts, the same depositions described above were done on SLG substrates.

Film and device characterization:

Cross-section micrographs of the finished devices were obtained by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) in an FEI Quanta 50 FEG SEM, to determine the thickness of the different layers. In addition, the thickness of the front contacts was also assessed by contact profilometry with the Tencor P-16 Surface Profiler. The optical transmittances and reflectance of the thin films on SLG were measured with a PerkinElmer LAMBDA 950 UV–VIS–NIR spectrophotometer coupled with an integrating sphere detector module. The optical bandgaps were determined by a sigmoid-Boltzmann fitting of the complete absorbance as a function of the energy following the equation $\alpha(E) = \alpha_{\max} + ((\alpha_{\min} - \alpha_{\max}) / (1 + \exp((E - E^{\text{Boltz}}) / \delta E)))$, where the direct bandgap is equal to $E_g = E^{\text{Boltz}} - 0.3 \delta E$. Here α corresponds to the absorption coefficient, while E^{Boltz} is the energy coordinate at which α is halfway between α_{\min} and α_{\max} ; and δE is associated with the slope of the sigmoid curve.²⁴

The crystal structure for the individual front contact, window stack, and full device were determined by X-ray diffraction (XRD) using Cu K α radiation in a Panalytical XPert PRO MRD processed in HighScore. Raman spectra were obtained with a power of 5 mW at 532 nm and an 1800-line grating with a Witec alpha300 R Confocal Raman Microscope. Transport properties of the front contact layers such as resistivity, mobility, and electron density were measured in a home-made Hall system at room temperature with a constant magnetic field of 0.6 T in a four-point Van der Pauw geometry with indium contacts.

The current density–voltage (JV) characteristics of solar cell devices were assessed in a solar simulator (Oriel Sol3A class AAA) under AM1.5 illumination. The devices,

manually scribed to $\sim 0.15 \text{ cm}^2$, were measured without a front grid at room temperature. To evaluate the external quantum efficiency (EQE) the QEX10 Solar Cell Quantum Efficiency Measurement (PV Measurement Inc.) was employed. A 75 W Xenon arc lamp served as a white light source to generate a monochromatic beam. Measurements were done in DC mode within a spectral range of 300 – 1100 nm. Internal quantum efficiency (IQE) spectra were derived from EQE data. The reflectance of the solar cells was measured by UV–vis NIR spectrophotometry with an integrated sphere detector module.

Results and discussion

Amorphous $\text{In}_2\text{O}_3\text{:H}$ (IOH) films present a low resistivity being 10 times more conductive than polycrystalline ZnO:Al (AZO) on soda-lime glass (SLG) (Table 1). In our previous work, we found that an annealing process increases the resistivity of our IOH films; therefore, in this work, we did not perform any kind of temperature treatment.²³ Table 1 shows the electrical parameters of both TCOs studied. IOH films present a high carrier mobility and concentration of $(6.7 \pm 4.8) \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $(2.3 \pm 1.7) \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, respectively. This high mobility has been related with the amorphous nature of the IOH films, in contrast with the high amount of grain boundaries defects in the case of c-axis oriented AZO.²⁵

Table 1: Thicknesses, electrical parameters, and optical bandgap energies of different ZnO:Al and IOH on SLG. The electric measurements were performed by Hall Effect at room temperature.

Parameter	ZnO:Al	$\text{In}_2\text{O}_3\text{:H}$
Thickness (nm)	304±66	273±54
Bandgap (eV)	3.464±0.003	3.5±0.3
Sheet resistance ($\Omega \text{ sq}^{-1}$)	119±64	23±3
Resistivity (m $\Omega \text{ cm}$)	3.4±1.8	0.64±0.8
Carrier mobility ($\text{cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	1.0±0.4	6.7±4.8
Carrier concentration (10^{21} cm^{-3})	1.1±0.4	2.3±1.7

The XRD patterns obtained for the TCO and the CdS (ZTO)/i-ZnO/AZO (IOH) stacks on SLG show peaks corresponding to ZnO (Figure 1a). As reported in the literature, the AZO grows with a c-axis orientation, related with the (002) peak. In addition, the IOH XRD pattern confirms the lack of crystallinity of this layer, as expected. Regarding the samples with ZTO buffer, additional peaks were observed, corresponding to different facets of ZnO that are favored when the Sn ions are present. These peaks are related with the planes (100), (101) and (110).¹² Figure 1b presents the transmittance and reflectance for the buffer/i-ZnO/TCO stacks. IOH-based stacks exhibit an average visual transmittance (AVT) of 75 and 79% for CdS- and ZTO-samples, respectively. On the other hand, AZO-based samples have an AVT of 83 and 86% for CdS- and ZTO-stacks, respectively. It's worth to mention that ZTO-based stacks show a higher transparency due to the larger bandgap of ZTO compared with that of CdS.

Figure 1: (a) XRD pattern for ZnO:Al (AZO) and In_2O_3 :H (IOH) thin films on SLG. (b) Transmittance and reflectance spectra, (c) XRD patterns, and (d) Raman spectra for the buffer/window stack on SLG.

Both TCOs present a bandgap similar to the ones reported in the literature, around 3.5 eV, making them good candidates for front contact layer applications. Their high transparency allows the light to pass through and interact effectively with the absorber.²⁶ These bandgaps were estimated based on the complete absorption and with a sigmoid-Boltzmann fitting (Figure S1) said to be immune to user biases that are reported for graphical methods like the Tauc Plot.²⁴ Figure 1d shows the Raman spectra for the TCOs and buffer/i-ZnO/TCO stacks. ZnO-based films show a broad band at 569 cm^{-1} related to two longitudinal modes, namely A_1 and E_1 . These modes have been related with oxygen vacancies and free charge carriers.²⁷ CdS-based stacks present a band at 302 cm^{-1} related with a longitudinal phonon.²⁸ On the other hand, amorphous IOH didn't show any band, which corroborates its non-crystalline nature. In_2O_3 -based films are reported to have several Raman active bands, corresponding to the phonon vibration of the BCC crystal structure, only after an annealing process.^{29,30}

SEM cross-section images of the devices show a conformal growth for both buffers and TCOs (Figure 2). ZTO buffer layers are almost 5 times thicker than CdS layers, with a thickness of (313 ± 28) and (65 ± 18) nm, respectively. Morphologically, it is also interesting that ZTO and AZO films have a different morphology with a columnar growth for the Al-doped layer and smaller grains for the Sn-doped film. The latter have been already reported, and it concurs with the XRD data, as Sn-doping inhibits the columnar growth of ZnO.¹²

Figure 2: Cross-section SEM images of finished solar cells with front contact layers of (a) CdS/i-ZnO/ZnO:Al, (b) CdS/i-ZnO/In₂O₃:H, (c) Zn_{1-x}Sn_xO_y/i-ZnO/ZnO:Al, and (d) Zn_{1-x}Sn_xO_y/i-ZnO/In₂O₃:H. The images are colored as a guidance for the viewer.

Raman spectra of the complete devices (Figure S2a) show a broad band with a maximum close to 174 cm⁻¹ which was attributed to the A₁ vibrational mode of CIGSe.³¹ Interestingly, the 569 cm⁻¹ band, related with ZnO longitudinal modes, is not observed for the complete devices even though this layer is on the top of the devices. Furthermore, CdS-based devices show a broad peak at 302 cm⁻¹ related to a CdS mode and another band at ~140 cm⁻¹, which has been associated with the existence of ordered vacancy compounds (OVCs).^{32,33} Nonetheless, we cannot assure the presence of OVCs as it was not observed by other characterization techniques.

XRD characterization of the complete devices (Figure S2b) exhibit the respective peaks and bands related to the presence of all the layers, except for the IOH layers which do not show any peaks confirming their amorphous state in the devices. Regarding ZnO-based layers, the peaks corresponding to planes (100) and (002) change in relative intensity due to the presence of the ZTO buffer layer, as expected due to the inhibition of the columnar growth by the presence of Sn.¹²

The performance of the solar cells was assessed by J-V measurements, from which the relevant parameters were extracted (Figure 3). For CdS-based devices, IOH as a front contact resulted in a slightly lower performance mainly related to lower J_{sc} values. The lower transparency of the CdS/i-ZnO/IOH stack compared with the AZO-based stacks (Figure 1b) is likely responsible for this loss in current, which is possibly related to a high refractive index for IOH thin films.²⁶ Nevertheless, it's worth noting that the fill factor for the IOH-based devices displays a narrower distribution with an average value of (69 ± 2) %. This improvement is closely related to an increase in the shunt resistance for IOH-based cells (Table S1 and S2), which minimizes current leakage pathways. Additionally, the improvement can be attributed to better electrical properties of IOH films compared with the AZO, contributing to a better overall device performance.

ZTO-devices show a slightly lower performance compared to CdS-reference cells with PCE of (10 ± 1) %, mostly associated with losses in FF and V_{oc}. It has been reported that ZTO cells prepared by CBD present a loss in V_{oc} probably related to a misalignment in the bands, which leads to recombination at the ZTO/CIGSe interface.¹² Nonetheless, ZTO/IOH devices show a slight improvement in V_{oc} compared to AZO-based cells, but further characterization is needed to understand

the reasons behind this phenomenon. In addition, this type of cell also exhibits a narrower PCE distribution compared to AZO-based stacks, which can be explained by a narrow FF distribution with an average value of $(61 \pm 2) \%$.

Figure 3: Solar cell parameters for CdS- and ZTO-based devices with ZnO:Al (AZO) and $\text{In}_2\text{O}_3\text{:H}$ (IOH) front contact layers: (a) power conversion efficiency (PCE), (b) short-circuit current density (J_{sc}), (c) fill factor (FF), and (d) open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}).

From JV curves of the champion cells of the studied devices, it can be seen that CdS-based devices show higher FF and V_{oc} compared with ZTO devices (Figure 4a). The latter has been related to misalignments in the bands between the absorber and the buffer, which do not allow the proper flow of the charge carriers.³⁴ Figure 4b shows the external quantum efficiency (EQE) spectra. High energy photons (with wavelengths less than 350 nm) are being absorbed for both front contacts with a bandgap around 3.5 eV. In the following wavelength range 400 – 500 nm, the difference between the buffers is clearly visible, with a strong parasitic absorption by the CdS layer. Between 600 and 1000 nm, the CdS/AZO cells show a higher EQE and weaker optical interferences, relative to ZTO/AZO devices. The strong optical interference for the ZTO-based can be attributed to their high reflectance. Indeed, the reflectance-corrected internal quantum efficiency (IQE) spectra (Figure S3a) do not show these features.

Figure 4: (a) JV curves and (b) external quantum efficiency (EQE) spectra for CdS- and ZTO-based devices with ZnO:Al (AZO) and $\text{In}_2\text{O}_3\text{:H}$ (IOH) front contact layers.

The CdS/IOH based champion cell shows a lower EQE for the whole range compared to the CdS/AZO standard device, while the literature for sputtered IOH front contacts only shows a low EQE for wavelength larger than 800nm.²⁶ Our results could be explained by the lower transmittance and higher reflectance of the IOH-stacks (see above). Interestingly, the ZTO/IOH champion cell displays a higher EQE than the ZTO/AZO device for photons with wavelength below 800 nm (better observed in the IQE, Figure S3a). Nonetheless, the explanation for this phenomenon requires further investigation of the optical interference within the ZTO/i-ZnO/IOH stack.

The fabricated devices were also stable under light illumination. No degradation was observed during the sample measurement. We performed a 30-minute light soaking treatment at 1 sun intensity, and no significant change was observed in the JV curves, as well as the associated parameters (Figure S4). This contrasts with the light instability that ZTO/IOH devices, fabricated by atomic layer deposition (ALD), present within the first minutes of illumination. The instability for ALD-based devices is related with a loss in V_{oc} , probably related to H-diffusion within the layers during the deposition.³⁵

Conclusions

The study demonstrates the potential of $\text{In}_2\text{O}_3\text{:H}$ (IOH) as a transparent conductive oxide layer for solar cell applications, offering improved electrical performance compared with ZnO:Al (AZO). IOH films show lower resistivity and higher carrier mobility, linked to their amorphous structure, which is likely reducing the impact of defects associated with grain boundaries. Both materials exhibited similar bandgaps around 3.5 eV, allowing effective light transmission for interaction with the photovoltaic absorber. However, IOH-based stacks presented lower transmittance compared with AZO, particularly in CdS-buffered configurations, likely due to differences in refractive index and optical properties.

Nevertheless, IOH-based devices show improvements in fill factor and narrower power conversion efficiency distributions, indicating consistent behavior across cells. For

ZTO-buffered configurations, IOH-based devices demonstrated a slight enhancement in open-circuit voltage over AZO, although the overall efficiency was slightly lower than CdS-based devices. Furthermore, our ZTO/IOH based devices are stable to illumination stimuli, in contrast to ALD-based devices reported in the literature. These results suggest that ZTO/IOH stacks, deposited by CBD and RF sputtering, respectively, offer significant advantages for photovoltaic applications. Moreover, further optimization of optical properties is needed to fully leverage their potential in high-performance solar cells.

Finally, this study also underscores the viability of using scalable and cost-efficient deposition techniques for both buffer and front contact layers in CIGSe solar cell technology. The performance achieved with these methods aligns well with that of conventional layers reported in the literature.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge support by the projects “Semi-TranspARent SOLar cells for building integrated photovoltaics (STAR-SOL)” (FCT-FNR/0001/2018) and “Designing superior CIGSe solar cells through understanding and controlling growth (Design-Solar)” (PTDC/CTM-CTM/2241/2021), both funded by FCT - Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, and by the project “Reusable Mask Patterning (REMAP), funded by the European Union under the European Innovation Council Pathfinder Open scheme (grant no. 101046909). M.A. thanks the Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT), Portugal for the PhD Grant (2020.06063.BD). We also thank the Nanophotonics and Bioimaging Facility (NBI) at the International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory (INL) for support.

References

- (1) Scheer, R.; Schock, H. *Chalcogenide Photovoltaics: Physics, Technologies, and Thin Film Devices*, 1st ed.; Wiley, 2011. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9783527633708>.
- (2) Salomé, P. M. P.; Rodriguez-Alvarez, H.; Sadewasser, S. Incorporation of Alkali Metals in Chalcogenide Solar Cells. *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells* **2015**, *143*, 9–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2015.06.011>.
- (3) Hedstrom, J.; Ohlsen, H.; Bodegard, M.; Kylner, A.; Stolt, L.; Hariskos, D.; Ruckh, M.; Schock, H.-W. ZnO/CdS/Cu(In,Ga)Se/Sub 2/ Thin Film Solar Cells with Improved Performance. *Conf. Rec. Twenty Third IEEE Photovolt. Spec. Conf. - 1993 Cat No93CH3283-9* **1993**, 364–371. <https://doi.org/10.1109/PVSC.1993.347154>.
- (4) Würfel, P.; Würfel, U. *Physics of Solar Cells: From Basic Principles to Advanced Concepts*; John Wiley & Sons, 2016.
- (5) Keller, J.; Stolt, L.; Törndahl, T.; Edoff, M. Silver Alloying in Highly Efficient CuGaSe₂ Solar Cells with Different Buffer Layers. *Sol. RRL* **2023**, *7* (12), 2300208. <https://doi.org/10.1002/solr.202300208>.
- (6) Barreau, N.; Frelon, A.; Lepetit, T.; Gautron, E.; Gautier, N.; Ribeiro-Andrade, R.; Nicoara, N.; Sadewasser, S.; Zabierowski, P.; Arzel, L.; Choubrac, L.; Harel, S.; Deudon, C.; Latouche, C.; Jobic, S.; Caldes, M.; Assmann, L.; Tsoulka, P.; Péan, E. V.; Lorthioir, J.; Geschier, F.; Braems, I.; Moret, M.; Briot, O.; Ouvrard, G. High Efficiency Solar Cell Based on Full PVD Processed Cu(In,Ga)Se₂/CdIn₂S₄

- Heterojunction. *Sol. RRL* **2017**, 1 (11), 1700140.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/solr.201700140>.
- (7) Lindahl, J.; Wätjen, J. T.; Hultqvist, A.; Ericson, T.; Edoff, M.; Törndahl, T. The Effect of Zn_{1-x}Sn_xO_y Buffer Layer Thickness in 18.0% Efficient Cd-Free Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ Solar Cells. *Prog. Photovolt. Res. Appl.* **2013**, 21 (8), 1588–1597.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/pip.2239>.
 - (8) Witte, W.; Hempel, W.; Paetel, S.; Menner, R.; Hariskos, D. Effects of Sputtered In_xS_y Buffer on CIGS with RbF Post-Deposition Treatment. *ECS J. Solid State Sci. Technol.* **2021**, 10 (5), 055006. <https://doi.org/10.1149/2162-8777/abfc21>.
 - (9) Witte, W.; Spiering, S.; Hariskos, D. Substitution of the CdS Buffer Layer in CIGS Thin-Film Solar Cells: Status of Current Research and Record Cell Efficiencies. *Vak. Forsch. Prax.* **2014**, 26 (1), 23–27. <https://doi.org/10.1002/vipr.201400546>.
 - (10) Montoya-Gómez, M.; Paetel, S.; Hempel, W.; Kanevce, A.; Magorian Friedlmeier, T.; Hariskos, D. Impact of Additives on the Chemical Bath Deposition of Zn(O,S) Used as Buffer Layer in High-Efficiency Cu(In,Ga)Se₂-Based Solar Cells. *Thin Solid Films* **2023**, 765, 139636.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsf.2022.139636>.
 - (11) Salomé, P. M. P.; Keller, J.; Törndahl, T.; Teixeira, J. P.; Nicoara, N.; Andrade, R.-R.; Stroppa, D. G.; González, J. C.; Edoff, M.; Leitão, J. P.; Sadewasser, S. CdS and Zn_{1-x}Sn_xO_y Buffer Layers for CIGS Solar Cells. *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells* **2017**, 159, 272–281.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2016.09.023>.
 - (12) Garzón, D. A.; Rossi, C.; Khatri, I.; Soggia, F.; Çaha, I.; Deepak, F. L.; Colombara, D.; Sadewasser, S. Chemical Bath Deposition of Zn_{1-x}Sn_xO_y Films as Buffer Layers for Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ Solar Cells. *Sol. RRL* **2023**, 7 (12), 2300173. <https://doi.org/10.1002/solr.202300173>.
 - (13) Larsson, F.; Nilsson, N. S.; Keller, J.; Frisk, C.; Kosyak, V.; Edoff, M.; Törndahl, T. Record 1.0 V Open-Circuit Voltage in Wide Band Gap Chalcopyrite Solar Cells. *Prog Photovolt Res Appl* **2017**, 25 (9), 755–763.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/pip.2914>.
 - (14) Minami, T.; Oohashi, K.; Takata, S.; Mouri, T.; Ogawa, N. Preparations of ZnO:Al Transparent Conducting Films by d.c. Magnetron Sputtering. *Thin Solid Films* **1990**, 193–194, 721–729. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0040-6090\(90\)90224-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0040-6090(90)90224-2).
 - (15) Chopra, K. L.; Major, S.; Pandya, D. K. Transparent Conductors—A Status Review. *Thin Solid Films* **1983**, 102 (1), 1–46. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0040-6090\(83\)90256-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0040-6090(83)90256-0).
 - (16) Cohen, M. L.; Chelikowsky, J. R. Chalcopyrite Structure Semiconductors. In *Electronic Structure and Optical Properties of Semiconductors*; Cohen, M. L., Chelikowsky, J. R., Eds.; Springer Series in Solid-State Sciences; Springer: Berlin, Heidelberg, 1988; pp 161–171. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-97080-1_10.
 - (17) Das, R.; Ray, S. Zinc Oxide—a Transparent, Conducting IR-Reflector Prepared by Rf-Magnetron Sputtering. *J. Phys. Appl. Phys.* **2002**, 36 (2), 152.
<https://doi.org/10.1088/0022-3727/36/2/312>.
 - (18) Koida, T.; Sai, H.; Kondo, M. In₂O₃:H Transparent Conductive Oxide Films with High Mobility and near Infrared Transparency for Optoelectronic Applications. *Surf. Eng.* **2012**, 28, 102–107.
<https://doi.org/10.1179/1743294411Y.0000000053>.

- (19) Koida, T.; Fujiwara, H.; Kondo, M. High-Mobility Hydrogen-Doped In₂O₃ Transparent Conductive Oxide for a-Si:H/c-Si Heterojunction Solar Cells. *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells* **2009**, *93* (6), 851–854. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2008.09.047>.
- (20) Koida, T.; Fujiwara, H.; Kondo, M. Hydrogen-Doped In₂O₃ as High-Mobility Transparent Conductive Oxide. *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys.* **2007**, *46* (7L), L685. <https://doi.org/10.1143/JJAP.46.L685>.
- (21) Igasaki, Y.; Kanma, H. Argon Gas Pressure Dependence of the Properties of Transparent Conducting ZnO:Al @lms Deposited on Glass Substrates. *Appl. Surf. Sci.* **2001**.
- (22) Fuster, D.; Anacleto, P.; Virtuoso, J.; Zutter, M.; Brito, D.; Alves, M.; Aparicio, L.; Fuertes Marrón, D.; Briones, F.; Sadewasser, S.; García, J. M. System for Manufacturing Complete Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ Solar Cells in Situ under Vacuum. *Sol. Energy* **2020**, *198*, 490–498. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2020.01.073>.
- (23) Alves, M.; Brito, D.; Carneiro, J.; Teixeira, V.; Sadewasser, S. Radio-Frequency Magnetron Sputtering Deposition Process for In₂O₃:H Transparent Conductive Oxide Films for Application in Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ Solar Cells. *Thin Solid Films* **2023**, *774*, 139840. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsf.2023.139840>.
- (24) Zanatta, A. R. Revisiting the Optical Bandgap of Semiconductors and the Proposal of a Unified Methodology to Its Determination. *Sci. Rep.* **2019**, *9* (1), 11225. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-47670-y>.
- (25) Koida, T.; Ueno, Y.; Nishinaga, J.; Higuchi, H.; Takahashi, H.; Iioka, M.; Shibata, H.; Niki, S. Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ Solar Cells with Amorphous In₂O₃-Based Front Contact Layers. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2017**, *9* (35), 29677–29686. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.7b07092>.
- (26) Witte, W.; Carron, R.; Hariskos, D.; Fu, F.; Menner, R.; Buecheler, S. IZO or IOH Window Layers Combined with Zn(O,S) and CdS Buffers for Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ Solar Cells. *Phys. Status Solidi A* **2017**, *214* (12), 1700688. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pssa.201700688>.
- (27) Kumar, K. D. A.; Valanarasu, S.; Kathalingam, A.; Ganesh, V.; Shkir, Mohd.; AlFaify, S. Effect of Solvents on Sol–Gel Spin-Coated Nanostructured Al-Doped ZnO Thin Films: A Film for Key Optoelectronic Applications. *Appl. Phys. A* **2017**, *123* (12), 801. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00339-017-1426-z>.
- (28) Nanda, K. K.; Sarangi, S. N.; Sahu, S. N.; Deb, S. K.; Behera, S. N. Raman Spectroscopy of CdS Nanocrystalline Semiconductors. *Phys. B Condens. Matter* **1999**, *262* (1), 31–39. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0921-4526\(98\)00474-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0921-4526(98)00474-8).
- (29) Ariyanto Wibowo Setia Budhi. Hydrogenated Indium Oxide (IO:H) for Thin Film Solar Cell. Master Thesis, Delft University of Technology, 2016. https://repository.tudelft.nl/file/File_2c97f152-d5c2-4039-bda0-87d6376f7a52?preview=1 (accessed 2024-11-29).
- (30) Dasari, S. G.; Nagaraju, P.; Yelsani, V.; Tirumala, S.; M V, R. R. Nanostructured Indium Oxide Thin Films as a Room Temperature Toluene Sensor. *ACS Omega* **2021**, *6* (27), 17442–17454. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.1c01831>.
- (31) Choi, I.-H. Raman Spectroscopy of CuIn_{1-x}Ga_xSe₂ for In-Situ Monitoring of the Composition Ratio. *Thin Solid Films* **2011**, *519* (13), 4390–4393. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsf.2011.02.058>.

- (32) Keller, J.; Stolt, L.; Sopiha, K. V.; Larsen, J. K.; Riekehr, L.; Edoff, M. On the Paramount Role of Absorber Stoichiometry in (Ag,Cu)(In,Ga)Se₂ Wide-Gap Solar Cells. *Sol. RRL* **2020**, *4* (12), 2000508. <https://doi.org/10.1002/solr.202000508>.
- (33) Suryavanshi, P. S.; Panchal, C. J. Low-Cost Fabrication of Single Chalcogenide CuInGaSe₂ Sputter Target and Its Thin Films for Solar Cell Applications. *J. Opt.* **2024**, *53* (2), 828–846. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12596-023-01324-5>.
- (34) Lindahl, J. Atomic Layer Deposition of Zinc Tin Oxide Buffer Layers for Cu(In, Ga)Se₂ Solar Cells. PhD Thesis, Acta Universitatis Upsaliensis, Uppsala, 2015.
- (35) Keller, J.; Stolt, L.; Edoff, M.; Törndahl, T. Atomic Layer Deposition of In₂O₃ Transparent Conductive Oxide Layers for Application in Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ Solar Cells with Different Buffer Layers. *Phys. Status Solidi A* **2016**, *213* (6), 1541–1552. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pssa.201532883>.